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Contraceptive knowledge and use pattern among female students in the college of health in the Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State.

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ABSTRACT

Contraceptive use is a critical component of reproductive health, particularly among young women in tertiary institutions who are at increased risk of unintended pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections. Despite relatively high awareness of contraception, utilization remains suboptimal in many low- and middle-income countries, including Nigeria. This study assessed the relationship between contraceptive knowledge and use patterns among female health students of Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State. A descriptive cross-sectional study design was employed among female undergraduate students in the College of Health Sciences, Niger Delta University. Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire assessing socio-demographic characteristics, contraceptive knowledge, patterns of use, and barriers to utilization. Knowledge and use patterns were analyzed using descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential tests at a 95% confidence level. A sample of **345 students** was calculated as the minimum sample, with an additional 10% (≈ 39) added to account for attrition, bringing the total enrolled to **384 participants**. Most respondents were aged 21–25 years and single. Awareness of contraceptives was high (89.8%), with over half demonstrating good or excellent knowledge. However, only 52.9% had ever used contraceptives, and consistent use was low. Fear of side effects, religious and cultural beliefs, privacy concerns, peer influence, and cost were major barriers. A positive relationship was observed between higher contraceptive knowledge and the likelihood of use.

Keywords : Contraceptives; Female Students; Niger Delta; Use Pattern; Bayelsa State.

Introduction :

Contraception refers to the deliberate use of methods or devices to prevent pregnancy by interfering with ovulation, fertilization, or implantation, and it remains a central component

of reproductive health and family planning. Modern contraceptive methods include implants, intrauterine devices (IUDs), injectables, oral contraceptive pills, male and female condoms, emergency contraceptive pills, and sterilization,

while traditional methods include withdrawal and periodic abstinence, which are generally less reliable due to higher failure rates. Access to safe and effective contraception enables individuals to make informed reproductive choices, prevent unintended pregnancies, reduce unsafe abortions, and improve maternal and child health outcomes. Beyond individual health benefits, contraceptive use contributes significantly to women's educational attainment, economic participation, and overall socio-economic development.

Globally, contraceptive use has increased over the past decades; however, substantial disparities persist across regions. Millions of women, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, continue to experience unmet need for family planning despite high levels of awareness. I

n sub-Saharan Africa, modern contraceptive prevalence remains comparatively low, contributing to elevated rates of unintended pregnancies and associated health risks. In Nigeria, modern contraceptive use is still limited, with significant gaps between awareness and consistent utilization. Factors such as myths and misconceptions about side effects, socio-cultural and religious opposition, gender power dynamics, low health literacy, and inadequate access to youth-friendly services contribute to this disparity.

Contraceptive knowledge plays a critical role in influencing attitudes and practices. Adequate knowledge encompasses awareness of different methods, their mechanisms of action, effectiveness, possible side effects, and correct usage.

Although awareness levels are often high, comprehensive understanding is not always guaranteed, and incomplete or incorrect information can undermine effective use. Misconceptions such as fears of infertility, cancer, or long-term health complications continue to discourage uptake and adherence to modern methods. In addition, confusion between methods that prevent pregnancy and those that protect against

sexually transmitted infections highlights the importance of accurate and comprehensive reproductive health education. Patterns of contraceptive use are shaped not only by knowledge but also by behavioral and structural factors. Inconsistent use, incorrect application, and reliance on less effective traditional methods reduce overall effectiveness and increase the risk of unintended outcomes.

Concerns about side effects, fear of social stigma, embarrassment in accessing services, lack of privacy, and financial constraints further limit sustained use. Cultural and religious norms may also influence perceptions of contraceptive acceptability, creating internal conflicts between biomedical understanding and social expectations.

The concept of dual protection: simultaneous prevention of unintended pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections is particularly important in reproductive health. While barrier methods such as condoms offer dual benefits, they are often used inconsistently, and individuals may rely on methods that prevent pregnancy without offering protection against infections. This gap underscores the need for integrated education and counseling that emphasizes both pregnancy prevention and infection control.

Overall, contraception remains a cornerstone of reproductive health and public health advancement. While awareness of contraceptive methods has improved considerably, significant gaps persist between knowledge and consistent, correct utilization. Addressing misconceptions, strengthening access to confidential and affordable services, and promoting comprehensive reproductive health education are essential steps toward improving contraceptive uptake and ensuring that individuals can exercise informed and autonomous reproductive choices.

The Main Objective of the Study :

This study assessed the relationship between contraceptive knowledge and use patterns among female health students of Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State.

Methods

Study Population: The study population consisted of female undergraduate students enrolled in the College of Health Science, including the Faculty of Pharmacy, Niger Delta University (NDU), Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State. This included students from disciplines such as Medicine, Nursing, Pharmacy, Medical Laboratory Science, Anatomy, Physiology, and Medical Biochemistry (Table 1).

Table 1: Participants distribution according to department and year of study (N=384)

Department	Medicine	51	13.3%
	Nursing	69	18.0%
	Pharmacy	48	12.5%
	Medical Laboratory Science	79	20.6%
	Anatomy	53	13.8%
	Physiology	45	11.7%
	Medical Biochemistry	39	10.2%
Level of Study	100	65	16.9%
	200	81	21.1%
	300	94	24.5%
	400	89	23.2%
	500	42	10.9%
	600	13	3.4%

Study Setting : The study was conducted at Niger Delta University (NDU), located in Wilberforce Island, Amassoma, Southern Ijaw Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. NDU is a state-owned institution established in 2000, with a student population of over 20,000. The univer-

sity has several faculties, including the College of Health Sciences, which houses various health-related programs. Wilberforce Island is semi-rural, with limited healthcare facilities, and the university provides a unique setting for studying reproductive health behaviors among students.

Study Design : This study adopted a cross-sectional descriptive design.

Research Instrument : A structured self-report questionnaire was designed, based on the objectives of the study. The questionnaire was written in English and made available as a physical copy. It was divided into four (4) sections: socio-demographics, knowledge of contraception, patterns

of contraceptive use, and barriers and challenges to contraceptive use. Supervisors and experienced experts in the field validated this study instrument. Self-report questionnaires are designed, pre-tested, and administered after validation.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Female students enrolled in health-related courses at NDU.
2. Undergraduate students across all levels of study.
3. Students who give informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Female students enrolled in non-health-related faculties.
2. Postgraduate students.
3. Students who decline to participate or withdraw consent during the study

Data Collection Tool : A self-report questionnaire was used.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of Niger Delta University. Informed consent was sought from each participant before data collection. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. No names or identifying infor-

mation were collected, and data were used strictly for academic purposes.

Sampling Calculation or Power Calculation

The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane formula (1967) for a finite population.

Using the Yamane formula: $n = N / [1 + N (e)^2]$; where

n = sample size

N = Population size

Sampling Techniques

In this study, a stratified random sampling method was used. This means the female students were first divided into groups (called strata) based on their departments (Medicine,

Data Analysis

The data generated was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27 and Microsoft

e = margin of error (commonly 0.05)

For a population of 2500, the calculation would be:

$$n = 2500 / [1 + 2500 (0.05)^2] = 2500 / (1 + 6.25) \approx 345$$

Therefore, a sample of **345 students** will be recruited, with an additional 10% (≈ 39) added to account for attrition, bringing the total to **384 participants**.

Nursing, Pharmacy, Medical Laboratory Science, etc.) and their levels of study (100–600 level). This way, all departments and levels were fairly represented in the study, making the results more reliable.

Excel. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) were used to summarize sociodemographic variables, knowledge levels, and contraceptive use patterns.

Table 2: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 384)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	Below 18	26	6.8
	18–20	123	32.0
	21–25	176	45.8
	Above 25	59	15.4
Marital Status	Single	358	93.2
	Married	21	5.5
	Others	5	1.3
Religion	Christianity	316	82.3
	Islam	52	13.5
	Traditional/Others	16	4.2
Monthly Allowance	< ₦10,000	101	26.3
	₦10,000–₦30,000	164	42.7
	₦31,000–₦50,000	77	20.1
	> ₦50,000	42	10.9

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 2 presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. The age distribution shows that most of the respondents were aged 21–25 years (45.8%), followed by those aged 18–20 years (32.0%), indicating that the majority were within the active reproductive age group. The majority of respondents were single (93.2%), which is relevant when assessing contraceptive knowledge and use patterns. Most

Knowledge of Contraceptives

Most respondents demonstrated high awareness of contraceptives (89.8%), with the majority correctly identifying their role in preventing pregnancy (78.4%). However, knowledge regarding protection against sexually transmitted infections was lower (68.5%), with notable proportions expressing un-

Use Patterns of Contraceptives

Slightly more than half of the respondents (52.9%) reported that they had used contraceptives, while 47.1% had never used any form of contraception. Among users, contraceptive use was mostly inconsistent, as only 18.8% reported always using contraceptives, whereas 22.4% used them sometimes and 11.7% used them rarely. Nearly half of the respondents

participants identified as Christians (82.3%), and in terms of monthly allowance, a large proportion received ₦10,000–₦30,000 (42.7%), indicating moderate financial capacity that may influence access to contraceptive services. Overall, the socio-demographic profile suggests a predominantly young, single, and academically advanced population suitable for assessing the relationship between contraceptive knowledge and use patterns among female health students of Niger Delta University.

certainty or incorrect understanding. Overall, 55.2% had good or excellent knowledge, while the rest showed fair to poor knowledge. Additionally, 64.3% were willing to recommend contraceptive use to peers, indicating a generally positive attitude. Despite high awareness, gaps remain—particularly regarding STI protection—which may affect contraceptive use patterns. This is shown in Table 3 below.

(47.1%) reported never using contraceptives. Regarding side effects, almost equal proportions of respondents reported experiencing side effects (49.0%) and not experiencing side effects (51.0%). These findings indicate moderate utilization of contraceptives among female health students, with inconsistent use patterns and concerns about side effects potentially influencing sustained contraceptive use. This is shown in Table 4 below.

Table 3: Knowledge of Contraceptives among Respondents (n = 384)

Item	Response	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Heard of contraceptives	Yes	345	89.8
	No	39	10.2
Do contraceptives prevent pregnancy?	Yes	301	78.4
	No	36	9.4
	Don't know	47	12.2
Do contraceptives prevent STIs?	Yes	263	68.5
	No	58	15.1
	Don't know	63	16.4
Overall knowledge	Good/Excellent	212	55.2
	Fair	108	28.1
	Poor/Very poor	64	16.7
Recommend to peers	Yes	247	64.3
	No	68	17.7
	Not sure	69	18.0

Table 4: Use Pattern of Contraceptives (n = 384)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Ever used contraceptives	Yes	203	52.9
	No	181	47.1
Frequency of use	Always	72	18.8
	Sometimes	86	22.4
	Rarely	45	11.7
	Never	181	47.1
Experienced side effects	Yes	188	49.0
	No	196	51.0

Table 5: Barriers and Challenges to Contraceptive Use (n = 384)

Barrier	Response	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Fear of side effects	Yes	192	50.0
	No	192	50.0
Religious/cultural beliefs	Yes	180	46.9
	No	204	53.1
Discouraging peer comments	Yes	151	39.3
	No	233	60.7
Embarrassment with providers	Yes	136	35.4
	No	248	64.6
Cost as a barrier	Yes	126	32.8
	No	258	67.2
Lack of privacy	Yes	142	37.0
	No	242	63.0

Table 6: Association between Knowledge of Contraceptives and Contraceptive Use (n = 384)

Knowledge Level	Used Contraceptives	Not Used	Total
Good knowledge	156	56	212
Poor knowledge	47	125	172
Total	203	181	384

$\chi^2 = 58.94$ df = 1 p < 0.001

Table 7: Association between Religious/Cultural Beliefs and Contraceptive Use (n = 384)

Religious Belief Influence	Used	Not Used	Total
Yes	64	116	180
No	139	65	204
Total	203	181	384

$\chi^2 = 47.63$ df = 1 p < 0.001

Table 8: Association between Fear of Side Effects and Contraceptive Use (n = 384)

Fear of Side Effects	Used	Not Used	Total
Yes	42	150	192
No	161	31	192
Total	203	181	384

$\chi^2 = 121.86$ df = 1 p < 0.001.

Table 9: Association between Knowledge of Contraceptives and Peer Recommendation (n = 384)

Knowledge Level	Recommend Use	Do Not Recommend	Total
Good knowledge	178	34	212
Poor knowledge	69	103	172
Total	247	137	384

$\chi^2 = 83.17$ df = 1 p < 0.001

Table 10: Association between Cost as a Barrier and Contraceptive Use (n = 384)

Cost Barrier	Used	Not Used	Total
Yes	46	80	126
No	157	101	258
Total	203	181	384

$\chi^2 = 12.48$ df = 1 p = 0.001

Discussion of Key Findings

The study reveals important findings regarding the relationship between contraceptive knowledge and use patterns among female health students of Niger Delta University. The majority of respondents were within the active reproductive age group, with 45.8% aged 21–25 years and 32.0% aged 18–20 years. Most participants were single (93.2%) and predominantly Christian (82.3%), with a large proportion at the 300 (24.5%) and 400 (23.2%) levels, indicating substantial academic exposure to health-related information. This demographic profile makes the population particularly suitable for assessing contraceptive knowledge and practice. Awareness of contraceptives was high, with 89.8% of respondents reporting that they had heard of contraceptives. Additionally, 78.4% correctly identified that contraceptives prevent pregnancy. However, knowledge regarding protection against sexually transmitted infections was lower, with 68.5% answering correctly, while 16.4% were unsure and 15.1% answered incorrectly. Overall, 55.2% of respondents demonstrated good or excellent knowledge, 28.1% had fair

knowledge, and 16.7% had poor or very poor knowledge. Furthermore, 64.3% indicated willingness to recommend contraceptives to peers, reflecting generally positive attitudes toward their use.

Despite relatively high knowledge levels, contraceptive utilization was moderate. Only 52.9% of respondents reported ever using contraceptives, while 47.1% had never used any method. Consistent use was low, as only 18.8% reported always using contraceptives, whereas 22.4% used them sometimes and 11.7% used them rarely. Nearly half of the respondents (49.0%) reported experiencing side effects, which may contribute to inconsistent use patterns. These findings highlight a clear knowledge–practice gap among the respondents.

The study further identified key barriers influencing contraceptive use. Fear of side effects was reported by 50.0% of respondents, making it the most prominent barrier. Religious and cultural beliefs affected 46.9% of participants, while discouraging peer comments influenced 39.3%. Embarrassment when accessing contraceptive services was reported by

35.4%, lack of privacy by 37.0%, and cost was considered a barrier by 32.8%. These findings demonstrate that both personal concerns and sociocultural factors significantly impact contraceptive behavior.

Conclusion

This study assessed the relationship between contraceptive knowledge and use patterns among female health students of Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State. The findings revealed that the majority of respondents were young, single women within the active reproductive age group and at advanced levels of study, making them an appropriate population for evaluating contraceptive knowledge and practices. Awareness of contraceptives was generally high, with most respondents demonstrating a good understanding of their role in preventing pregnancy. However, gaps in knowledge were identified, particularly regarding protection against sexually transmitted infections and correct, consistent use.

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Conflict of Interest

The researchers declare that there was no conflict of interest.

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Overall, the findings demonstrate that although contraceptive knowledge is relatively high among female health students, utilization remains inconsistent and is strongly influenced by psychosocial and structural barriers.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that while contraceptive knowledge among female health students is relatively high, this does not consistently translate into optimal use. Addressing misconceptions about side effects, strengthening youth-friendly and confidential reproductive health services, and promoting culturally sensitive counseling are essential steps toward improving contraceptive uptake and consistency. Integrating comprehensive contraceptive counseling into student health services and leveraging peer education strategies may further enhance informed decision-making and contribute to improved reproductive health outcomes among female university students.

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